

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF PROMISING LOCAL FODDER VARIETIES OF GRAPES

Fayziev Jamoliddin Nasirovich

d.a.sc, s.r.f

Kurbanova Sarvinoz Anvar kizi

junior research fellow

Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named after

M. Mirzaev

Academician

Mansurova Mukhlisa Akromkhan kizi

master

Kholboev Kamoliddin Fakhriddin ugli

master

Tashkent State Agrarian University

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Annotation. The article examines the chemical composition of promising local food varieties of grapes. Grape head, cluster weight, and mechanical composition of the Said Gulyam, Husayni bride's finger, Kara Djanjal and Husayni Bely varieties of grapes are described.

Keywords: grape, variety, dry matter, glucose, fructose, additive, acidity.

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрен химический состав перспективных местных столовых сортов винограда. Описаны головки винограда, масса грозди и механический состав сортов винограда Саид Гулям, Хусайни палец невесты, Кара Джанжал и Хусайни Белый.

Ключевые слова: виноград, сорт, сухое вещество, глюкоза, фруктоза, Вяжущие вещества, кислотность.

Introduction: Seedless varieties of grapes have been grown by the people of the republic since ancient times and consumed as a valuable product. Therefore, the creation of seedless varieties of grapes has a special place both in folk breeding and in scientific breeding. Today, scientists are conducting a lot of research on the creation of such varieties of grapes, and some progress is being made.

Forage varieties of grapes, as in many other fruit and berry crops, are a positive sign in any application of the product.

It should be noted that the value of new varieties is primarily determined by the mechanical properties and chemical composition of the grapes. A detailed knowledge of the chemical composition and characteristics of the grape head and stem of each newly created grape variety determines its consumption characteristics and allows for their effective use in the technological processes of

processing. Because, firstly, the consumption qualities of fresh grapes depend on the size of the bunch of grapes, the consistency of the flesh, the amount of sugar in the content, secondly, in technical varieties, the juice extracted for wine is separated in several stages according to the mechanical composition of the grape cluster, and finally, thirdly, the quality of promising local food varieties also directly depends on the mechanical properties of the grape cluster, sugar content and sugar content [4; 53-57; 5; 5-24]

Scientific research method. Field experiments were conducted in the grape collection and experimental fields of the Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named after Makhmud Mirzaev.

The sugar content of grape juice was determined with a hydrometer indicating the specific gravity of the juice.

Acidity was determined using the titration method in 0.1 N alkali solution (NaON) with the addition of phenolphthalein as an indicator to grape juice.

Research results. The analysis shows that scientific research observations were made to study the chemical composition of the main grape head in promising local food grape varieties.

The chemical composition of grape head juice of promising local food grape varieties was differentiated. In production, the chemical composition of the grape heads is of great importance. From the analysis, it was found that the most dry matter clusters (29.8-28.2%) were found in Said Gulyam and Husayni bride's finger varieties of grapes.

The group with low dry matter (27.1-22.2%) was made up of Husayni Bely and Kara Djanjal grape varieties.

Total sugar content also differed by variety. The Kara Djanjal grape variety stood out with its high sugar content (26.0%). Husayni Bely grape variety had the lowest sugar content (18.25%). The amount of sugar in the clusters of the remaining varieties was 23.1-21.9%.

The highest glucose content (13.2-12.7%) was found in Kara Djanjal and Said Gulyami grape varieties (see Table 3).

Table 3

Chemical composition of grape head juice of promising local food varieties of grapes, 2020-2022

o/ n	Sorts	dry matter, %	Sugar, %			Astringe nt substanc es,%	Acidity, g/l
			General	Of that glucos e	fructos e		

1.	Said Gulyami	29,8	21,9	12,7	9,2	0,0985	5,4
2.	Husain bride finger	28,2	23,1	12,4	11,7	0,0915	4,8
3.	Kara janjal	22,2	26,0	13,2	12,8	0,0584	4,0
4.	Hussain bely	27,1	18,25	11,0	7,25	0,0507	4,65

The highest acidity (5.4%) was found in the bunches of the Said Gulyami grape variety. The lowest acidity - 4.0% was recorded in the Kara djanjal variety. In the remaining grape varieties - Husayni belyy and Husayni bride finger varieties, this indicator was 4.65-4.8%.

Astringent substances are low in the clusters, their amount is 0.0507-0.0985%.

Summary

1. The chemical composition of the juice of grape heads of promising local food varieties of grapes was mutually differentiated. From the analysis, it was found that the most dry matter clusters (29.8-28.2%) were found in Said Gulyam and Husayni bride's finger varieties of grapes.

Total sugar content also differed by variety. The Kara Djanjal grape variety stood out with its high sugar content (26.0%). Husayni Bely grape variety had the lowest sugar content (18.25%). The amount of sugar in the clusters of the remaining varieties was 23.1-21.9%.

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